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Research Article

DEPRESSION AMONG FEMALES BECAUSE OF INFERTILITY¹Dr Batool Syeda, ²Dr Farhat Abbas, ³Dr Saif Ullah¹Senior Lecturer, Department of Community Medicine, People's University of Medical and Health Sciences Nawabshah, Sindh²Allied Hospital Faisalabad³Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi

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Abstract:

Objectives: Childlessness is a state of highly depression which have a very bad effect on the married and social life of couple. Despair, unease & stress linked with the childlessness can affect the therapy and results for those childless couples. The main aim of this research work is to discover the occurrence of depression, worry & despair among the infertile females.

Methodology: Exact 100 infertile females and one hundred females as healthy controls chosen from department of gynecology of Allied Hospital Faisalabad were the participants of this research work. Women with mental problems and infertile male were not the part of this research work. Authentic version of DASS (Depression, Anxiety & Stress Scale) in Urdu language was in utilization for the evaluation of the scores of depression, stress & anxiety. The comparison of the outcomes from the patients and control members carried out the analysis of the result carried out with the help of T test.

Results: We found a high occurrence of despair, worry & stress among infertile females in comparison with the females of the healthy controls. There was no optimistic effect of the qualification on the scores of depression and anxiety. In the same manner, we found the same outcomes when the occupation of the females who were suffering from infertility utilized for stratified examination.

Conclusion: Stress, anxiety & depression are very frequent in infertile females. Professionals of the healthcare department should recommend the mental and help of a psychiatrist if needed, when they are advising the treatment of the fertility for the suffering females.

KEY WORDS: Therapy, Depression, Inability, Mental Health, Victims, Anxiety, Infertility Stress.

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INTRODUCTION:

The most wanted wish of the couple is to have baby but inability to get child in spite of continuous sex for a complete one year is infertility. The infertility occurrence rate is different in various part of the world and it is dependent on the cultural & matrimonial values [1]. It is an estimation that ten percent couples are suffering from this disorder because of various causes and in most of the cases, the main cause remains not known [2]. It is very common for a couple which is infertile to suffer from the problems of mental health. The range of the approximate occurrence of the problems of the mental health is from 30.0% to 80.0% according to different research works & it has association to the cause of infertility and the period of infertility and total quantity of the amount of various therapy options [3-5].

Mental complications due to this problem can be from the complex of inferiority & stress to the serious despair & anxiety [6, 7]. Females are mostly the victims of this mental suffering, particularly, in those regions where, there is a consideration that females are the main part of inability of bearing a child among couple. The qualification & the occupation of the female member are also effective aspects [1, 6, 8, 9]. In various communities as in Muslim communities, infertility is very despairing for the females because the culture and religion in this society permit the men to have four wives a single time and infertility of the female partner gives a strong reason to male o remarry [10]. Men of our country often oppressed to remarry if they have an infertile partner which creates mental problem for females. The occurrence of the mental complications among the females of our country are not the part of regular studies so far. Therefore, this research work carried out to evaluate the scores of stress, anxiety & depression among the females suffering from infertility.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work carried out at Allied Hospital Faisalabad. The duration of this study was from August 2018 to February 2019. One hundred infertile females were the part of this research work. One hundred fertile females with the infertile females during checkups were also the part of this research work as healthy controls. The females whose males were infertile or having some mental issues were not the part of this case work. All the participants gave the written consent to participate in the research work. All the information of demography, age qualification and family pressure gathered from the participants. DASS (depression, anxiety stress scale) was in utilization for

the collection of data about the mental effects due to infertility.

Depression Anxiety Stress			
Normal	0-9	0-7	0-14
Mild	10-13	8-9	15-18
Moderate	14-20	10-14	19-25
Severe	21-27	15-19	26-33
Extremely Severe	28+	20+	34+

A DASS of Urdu version with 42 items was in use for the measurements of the despair, anxiety and stress. Scores range of each item was from 0 to 3 or no signs to severity level. The calculation of the sum scores of every emotional condition carried out separately [11]. Chi square test method was in use for the analysis of the variables.

RESULTS:

Majority of the patients of this research work was from 20 to 30 year of age with 63.50% & second most frequent age group was from 31 to 40 years with a percentage of 31.50. We found a high rate of the education in both study groups. The persons with no qualification were 19 & 38 in study group and healthy controls accordingly. The housewives were available with very high percentage as 80% & 71% in controls and case group respectively, 2nd in number were employees as 18% & 21% and less frequent were the self-employed as 2% & 8% respectively. Outcome display that 79.0% patients suffering from infertility found with some amount of depression & 49.0% patients of the case group found with medium to serious amount of depression & ten percent patients found with severe depression. This was very high value as compared to the healthy controls. The average scores of depression in healthy controls was 3.9 ± 4.1650 & in the case group it was 16.140 ± 8.304 .

The average scores of anxiety in the case group was 14.630 ± 8.0850 in comparison with the healthy controls which was 3.690 ± 3.24 . 41.0% percent patients of the case group had medium to serious anxiety & 29.0% found with anxiety of severe nature but there was no case of severe anxiety in the healthy controls. These scores were also high in the case group with an average score of 19.720 ± 9.192 as compared to the healthy controls as average scores of 5.870 ± 4.952 . Only 5.0% persons of the healthy controls found with mild stress & no other high degree was available in the

healthy controls. About 69.0% persons of the case group found with stress (14.0% with mild, 21.0% with moderate and 29.0% with stress of serious nature).

Characteristic		Assigned Study Group	
		Control Group (n)	Study Group (n)
Age Group	20-30	63.0	64.0
	31-40	28.0	35.0
	> 40	9.0	1.0
Years of Education	Uneducated	38.0	19.0
	10 years or below	39.0	23.0
	12-14 years	23.0	40.0
	16 years or above	0.0	18.0
Occupation	House wife	71.0	80.0
	Employed	21.0	18.0
	Self Employed	8.0	2.0

Classification		Mean	SD	p-value
Depression	Control Group	3.900	4.17	0
	Study Group	16.140	8.30	
Anxiety	Control Group	3.690	3.24	0
	Study Group	14.630	8.09	
Stress	Control Group	5.870	4.95	0
	Study Group	19.720	9.19	

DISCUSSION:

This research work carried out to discover the amount of the despair, worry stress among infertile females at a tertiary hospital. This disorder is a disaster for a couple of our country because of some familial reasons. It is the dream of every couple to have children. In some families, it is very much important to have babies in very early stage of the marriage. A female has to suffer a lot if she is infertile because it provides a reason to the male to get another female for marriage which is not frequent in our society. This cultural and social pressure is the main cause of the development of the abnormal psychological signs in the females which are infertile. Al-hassan A concluded that about 62.0% females with infertility found with depression [1] in the city of Ghana. In the same manner, Guerra D concluded the occurrence of depression in the females of China as 69.9% who were suffering from this problem. The depression occurrence was 79.0% in this research work which is much greater than the above mentioned two case studies. This high occurrence was due to the religion, social and cultural norms which permit the man to have more than one wife and wife suffering from infertility provide them a reason to move on for another marriage. Having a male child gives confidence, pride & security to the females.

There is also a rate of the depression among the females suffering from infertility as stated from Japan [2] & Gambia [13]. This research work displayed that 70.0% females with infertility found with a varying rate of anxiety & 58.0% among these females found with medium to serious anxiety. Lawson, Allen HT &

Kraaji V concluded very high amount of anxiety in the subjects who were getting the treatment to get rid of infertility [14-16]. In the same manner, the scores of stress were also high in the females with infertility as concluded by Luk BH, Dooley & El Kissi. These findings are very much similar to the outcome of this case study [3, 4, 17]. One amazing outcome of this research work was that the scores of depressions, stress & anxiety were not depending upon the qualification of the females with infertility. This outcome is in contrast with the finding of Al-hassan [1], who concluded that the higher scores were present in the females with less or without education. This was a prospective research work which was a restriction of this research work. Due to this limitation, the results of this research work are not favorable for generalization.

CONCLUSION:

The outcome of this research work shows that there is a prevalence of high scores of stress, depression & anxiety among the females who are suffering from infertility. Further research works with the comparison of the stress among the patients is necessary to generalize the results of this research work.

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